

State Reduction for Semi-Markov Reliability Models

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Abstract

Semi-Markov processes have proved to be an effective and convenient tool to construct models of systems that achieve reliability by redundancy and reconfiguration. These models are able to depict complex system architectures and to capture the dynamics of fault arrival and system recovery. A disadvantage of this approach is that the models can be extremely large, which poses both a model construction and a computational problem. Techniques are needed to reduce the model size. Because these systems are used in critical applications where failure can be expensive, there must be an analytically derived bound for the error produced by the model reduction technique. Automatic model generation programs have been written to help the reliability analyst produce models of complex systems. Because of the importance of these programs, the model reduction technique needs to be precise and easily implemented. This paper presents a model reduction technique called trimming that can be applied to a popular class of systems. An error bound for the trimming procedure is derived that uses readily available system parameters. The trimming procedure is precisely described and appears easy to implement in a model generation program.

Introduction

Efforts are being made to design reliable digital control systems using redundancy and reconfiguration. The reliability requirement for these systems can be extremely high. An example is the proposed requirement that the flight control system for a commercial aircraft have less than one chance in a billion of failure during a ten hour flight. Such requirements are beyond what can be established by natural life testing. An alternate method that is being considered is to estimate the probability of system failure with a semi-Markov model that captures the elements of system architecture, component failure, and system recovery from failed components. A description of the system architecture arises from considering the components and how they are arranged. The component failure rate is obtained from field data. The description of system recovery from failed components comes from fault-injection experiments in the laboratory. These three features can be studied separately and then combined to form the reliability model for the system. Semi-Markov processes with their states representing the states of the system and their transitions between states representing fault occurrences and system recoveries have proved to be an effective and convenient reliability estimation tool.

A major obstacle is that a reconfigurable system of moderate size and complexity can generate an enormous semi-Markov model. This produces both a model construction problem and a computational problem. The model construction problem has become severe enough that programs have been written to automatically generate reliability models. These automatic model generators

have augmented the computational problem since it is now possible to produce models of extremely complex systems.

Sound and effective procedures are needed for model reduction. Since these models describe systems that need to be highly reliable, an acceptable model reduction method must have an analytically derived error bound. Because of the importance of automatic model generation, the method must be easy to implement and the error bound easy to compute. We believe the procedure offered here is a procedure that satisfies these requirements.

We call the procedure model-reduction-by-trimming or just trimming. The next section illustrates trimming by means of a concrete example. The third section gives a precise definition of trimming and a precise statement of the theorem for the error bound on trimming. The fourth section reviews the published mathematical result needed to derive the trimming bound, and the fifth section derives the bound. A sixth section shows that not all models can be trimmed and still yield an accurate estimate of reliability. It is essential to have a result on the error produced by trimming. A final section offers concluding remarks.

Illustrative Example

This section uses a simple example to illustrate the basic ideas of model reduction by trimming. This example is not completely realistic in engineering terms, but it covers the ideas in a concrete manner. Suppose a system consists of four central processor units, four memories, and four buses. In the initial configuration, three components of each type are active while the fourth is a cold spare. If a component becomes faulty, it is replaced by a spare. If the number of good processors, or good memories, or good buses falls below three, then the entire system goes into a simplex configuration consisting of one processor, one memory, and one bus. In this simplex configuration, the failure of any of the three components causes system failure. The initial configuration, showing just the active components, is displayed in Figure 1.

The system begins an operation cycle with each of the active processors requesting data from the memories. Each memory chooses a single bus (one bus per memory), and each memory sends data to all three processors. Each processor votes on the received data and performs its calculations. After computing, each processor chooses one bus (one bus per processor), and each processor sends data to all three memories. An operation cycle ends when each memory votes and stores the data.

There is some critical coupling between the processors and buses in the sense that the system can have a coincident-fault failure when one fault is in a processor and the other fault is in a bus. For example, suppose the processors are sending data to the memories with processor i using bus i for $i = 1, 2, 3$. If processor 1 and bus 2 are faulty, then the memory voters can be overwhelmed by incorrect data. However, if

Figure 1: Original Configuration of Processors, Memories and Buses

processor 1 and bus 1 are faulty, then the memories will vote correctly. Similarly, there is some critical coupling between the memories and the buses. There is no critical coupling between the processors and the memories.

Part of the reliability model for this system is shown in Figure 2. The failure rates for processors, memories, and buses are λ_p , λ_m , and λ_b respectively. For convenience, the system recoveries are assumed to be constant rate transitions with F_p , F_m , and F_b the system recovery rates for processors, memories, and buses. The mnemonics are A for a fault-free state, R for a single-fault recovery-mode state, V for a multiple-fault recovery-mode state, and X and Y for system failure states.

To illustrate model reduction by trimming, consider state R_p of Figure 2 where one of the active processors has become faulty. The recovery transition F_p removes this faulty processor and replaces it with the spare. The transition $2\lambda_p + 2\lambda_b$ represents the failure of another processor or of a bus that is critically coupled to the failed processor. The state X represents system failure because of coincident faults. The transitions $2\lambda_m$, λ_m , and λ_b represent fault arrival in components that are not critically coupled to the faulty processor. It seems reasonable to think that these last three transitions and their subsequent states can be ignored with negligible loss of accuracy, because even after these transitions there must be another component failure before there is system failure. We will call such states as R_p recovery-mode states. Model reduction by trimming eliminates all component failure transitions from recovery-mode states that do not cause immediate system failure.

Two models, complete and trimmed, were constructed for this system using the ASSIST reliability model generator [2]. The complete model contains 227 states and took 7878 seconds to compute. The trimmed model

contains 83 states and took 258 seconds to compute. Different methods of constructing a reliability model can produce equivalent models with different numbers of states, but the relative difference between the complete and trimmed model is likely to remain the same. For the parameter values, given as rates per hour,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_p &= 10^{-4} \\ \lambda_m &= 5 \times 10^{-4} \\ \lambda_b &= 10^{-5} \\ F_p &= 10000 \\ F_m &= 1000 \\ F_b &= 1000 \end{aligned}$$

and an operating time of $T=1$ hour the complete model returns

$$P\{\text{failure of complete model}\} = 1.80803726 \times 10^{-9}$$

while the trimmed model returns

$$P\{\text{failure of trimmed model}\} = 1.80803714 \times 10^{-9}.$$

Jumping ahead, the error bound for trimming (which will be derived below) is

$$TRMBND = \theta\mu (e^{\theta T} - \theta T - 1)$$

where

θ = maximum sum of the rates for the failure transitions leaving any state

μ = largest average holding time for all recovery-mode states

T = operating time.

For this example,

Figure 2: Reliability Model for the Illustrative Example

$\theta = 18.3 \times 10^{-4}/\text{hour}$
 $\mu = 10^{-3}$ hours
 $T = 1$ hour

and the computed error bound is

$$\text{TRMBND} = 3.066 \times 10^{-12}.$$

Thus, the actual error produced by model trimming is approximately one part in ten million, while the error bound for model trimming is approximately one part in a thousand. The results for this example are typical for an application of trimming. The number of states in the reliability model is reduced by about half. The computational effort is reduced by about an order of magnitude. The actual error from trimming is insignificant. The derived error bound for trimming is much larger than the actual error, but the derived error bound is still small compared to the computed probability of failure for the system.

Precise Description of Model Trimming

The bound for the error caused by trimming has been established for a popular class of systems, which we now describe. A common approach to achieving reliability is to have three or four components perform a majority vote. When a component becomes faulty and disagrees with the majority, it is discarded from the system and replaced by a spare if a spare is available. There are two failure modes. There is a coincident-fault failure when the voter is overwhelmed because a second component becomes faulty before a first faulty component can be removed. There is an exhaustion-of-parts failure when the number of good components falls below a minimum level. Almost all systems currently being considered

are assemblages of subsystems where each subsystem is a majority-voting system of the type described above.

For this class of systems, a reliability model has normal-operating states where all faulty components (if any) have been removed from the system, recovery-mode states where a faulty component has not yet been removed from the system, and absorbing states where the system has failed due to coincident faults or exhaustion of parts. We examine the recovery-mode states more closely. There are three types of transitions out of a recovery-mode state. The first type of transition represents system recovery. The second type of transition represents the failure of another component that causes immediate system failure (either coincident-fault or exhaustion-of-parts). The third type of transition represents the failure of another component that does not cause immediate system failure. That is, the third type of transition is not a transition to a system failure state. Model reduction by trimming is accomplished by removing all transitions of the third type (and their subsequent states) from the model.

Statement of Theorem

After the illustrative example and the discussion above, we can give an abbreviated list of assumptions.

1. Components fail at a low constant rate.
2. Fault recovery depends only on the time since fault occurrence.
3. The system is an assemblage of subsystems, where each subsystem achieves fault tolerance by a three-way or four-way majority voter.
4. All transitions to system failure are component failure transitions. (This assumption eliminates pathological cases.)

Figure 3: A General Path in a Semi-Markov Reliability Model

For each state i in the reliability model let θ_i be the sum of the component failure rates out of state i . Let θ be the maximum value among the θ_i . Let μ_j be the average holding time in recovery-mode state R_j . Let μ be the maximum value among the μ_j . Let T be the system operating time. An error bound for model reduction by trimming is given by

$$\text{TRMBND} = \theta \mu (e^{\theta T} - \theta T - 1).$$

The Algebraic Upper Bound

The error bound for model reduction by trimming is obtained from a theorem that places an upper bound on the probability of traversing a path in a semi-Markov reliability model by time T [1,3]. In such a model, the component failures are assumed to occur at a low constant rate, and system recovery is allowed to be a fast (arbitrary) distribution that depends only on the time elapsed since component failure. A general path in such a semi-Markov reliability model is shown in Figure 3. The global time-independence of a semi-Markov process permits the rearrangement of states on the path for notational and computational convenience [1,3]. In Figure 3, small Greek letters represent slow constant-rate failure transitions, while capital Roman letters represent fast system recovery transitions. The first line in Figure 3 contains the states with only slow constant-rate failure transitions. In the second line, the successful (on-path) transitions are the fast recovery transitions competing against slow constant-rate fault transitions and possibly other fast transitions. In the third line, the successful (on-path) transitions are the slow fault occurrences competing against one or more recoveries and possibly

other fault transitions. For notation, let

$Q(T)$ = probability of reaching state B_1 by time T

$P(F_i)$ = probability that $F_{i,1}$ is successful

$\mu(H_j)$ = mean of holding time in state C_j considering only recovery transitions.

An upper bound for the probability of traversing the path in Figure 3 by time T is

$$\frac{\lambda_1 \cdot \lambda_2 \dots \lambda_k T^k}{k!} \prod_{i=1}^m P(F_i) \prod_{j=1}^n \alpha_j \mu(H_j).$$

Derivation of the Trimming Bound

The general model for using the algebraic upper bound to derive the trimming bound is shown in Figure 4. This general model displays all the paths to the system failure states which are in a reliability model for the class of system we are considering. Hence the diagram in Figure 4 is dense in notation. This notation is necessary to index all the paths.

The system starts in state A which is a fault-free state. In this initial state, some components failures can take the system immediately to system failure. These component failures are represented by the transition ϵ to the system failure state X . Other components fail with rates $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$ and take the system to recovery-mode states R_1, \dots, R_n . From each of the states R_j , the diagram displays the three types of transitions out of a recovery-mode state discussed above. The ϵ transitions into X are the component

Figure 4: Path Diagram for the Proof of The Trimming Bound

failures that cause immediate system failure. The transitions from recovery-mode states, which are labeled F, to fault-free states represent the possible recovery actions the system can have.

The γ transitions represent the component failures out of a recover-mode state that do not cause immediate system failure. After a γ transition, three simplifying assumptions increase the computed probability of system failure (compared to the actual probability of system failure). The first assumption is that after a γ transition, the system is no longer able to remove failed components from the system. The second assumption is that after a γ transition, any other component failure causes immediate system failure. The third assumption is that this last transition occurs at rate θ which is the largest possible rate for a transition to a failure state.

Returning to the main sequence of component failure and system recovery, the recovery transitions F out of the states R go to the fault-free states B where the cycle of component failure and system recovery begins again.

An upper bound is obtained for the probability of being in state Y1 in figure 4 by considering all the paths to this failure state. One such path is the three step transition from A_0 to R_i by α_i , from R_i to $V_{i,j}$ by $\gamma_{i,j}$, and from $V_{i,j}$ to Y1 by θ . An upper bound for traversing this path by time T is

$$[\alpha_i T] [\gamma_{i,j} \mu] \left[\theta \frac{T}{2} \right]$$

where a slow failure transition competing against other failure transitions contributes the first factor, a slow failure transition competing against recovery transitions when the holding time in the recovery-mode

state is $\leq \mu$ contributes the second factor, and a second slow failure transition contributes the third factor. Summing over the fan-out from A_0 and the fan-outs from the R_i 's gives

$$\begin{aligned} Y1 &\leq \sum_i \sum_j \left\{ \alpha_i \gamma_{i,j} \mu \frac{T^2}{2!} \right\} \\ &\leq \theta \mu \frac{T^2}{2!} \sum_i \alpha_i \left[\sum_j \gamma_{i,j} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Since the sum of the failure rates out of any state is $\leq \theta$,

$$Y1 \leq \theta \mu \frac{T^2 \theta^2}{2!}.$$

A typical path from A_0 to Y2 has the five transitions from A_0 to R_i by α_i , from R_i to $B_{i,j}$ by $F_{i,j}$, from $B_{i,j}$ to $S_{i,j,k}$ by $\beta_{i,j,k}$, from $S_{i,j,k}$ to $V_{i,j,k,m}$ by $\gamma_{i,j,k,m}$, and from $V_{i,j,k,m}$ to Y2 by θ . An upper bound for traversing this path by time T is

$$[\alpha_i T] [P\{F_{i,j}\}] \left[\beta_{i,j,k} \frac{T}{2} \right] [\gamma_{i,j,k,m} \mu] \left[\theta \frac{T}{3} \right]$$

Summing over all the fan-outs gives

$$Y_2 \leq \sum_{ijkl} \{ \alpha_i P\{F_{i,j}\} \beta_{i,j,k} \gamma_{i,j,k,m} \mu \theta \frac{T^3}{3!} \}$$

$$\leq \theta \mu \frac{T^3}{3!} \sum_i \alpha_i \left\{ \sum_j P\{F_{i,j}\} \left[\sum_k \beta_{i,j,k} \left(\sum_m \gamma_{i,j,k,m} \right) \right] \right\}$$

Since the sum of the failure rates is $\leq \theta$, and the sum of the probabilities for the recovery transitions $F_{i,j}$ is ≤ 1 ,

$$Y_2(T) \leq \theta \mu \frac{T^3 \theta^3}{3!}$$

In general,

$$Y_k(T) \leq \theta \mu \frac{T^{k+1} \theta^{k+1}}{(k+1)!}$$

Summing all these bounds for the Y_k 's gives a trimming bound of

$$TRMBND \leq \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} Y_k(T) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \theta \mu \frac{T^{k+1} \theta^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} = \theta \mu (e^{\theta T} - \theta T - 1)$$

An Example with a Large Error Bound

This example shows that a theorem on the error produced by trimming is necessary since trimming does not always have a negligible effect. Consider a system consisting of four reconfigurable four-plexes. Each four-plex removes itself from the system when the four-plex recovers from the second fault occurrence in that four-plex. The system fails by exhaustion of parts when all four four-plexes have removed themselves from the system. The system fails by a coincident-fault failure if any four-plex has a coincident-fault failure. In addition, all reconfiguration ceases if there are two faults present in two different four-plexes. In this case the system fails upon the occurrence of a third fault anywhere in the system. For a component failure rate of 10^{-4} per hour, a recovery rate of 10^3 per hour, and an operating time of 700 hours, the error bound for trimming is 1.5×10^{-6} . The computed probability of system failure using the complete model is 1.16×10^{-6} . The computed probability of system failure using a trimmed model is 7.05×10^{-7} .

Concluding Remarks

This paper has presented a method of model reduction called trimming and has derived an error bound for this method of reducing the number of states in a semi-Markov reliability model. The error bound uses only three parameters from the semi-Markov model--the maximum sum of rates for failure transitions leaving any state, the maximum average holding time for a recovery-mode state, and the operating time for the system. The error bound can be computed before any model generation takes place which means the modeler can decide immediately whether or not the model can be trimmed. The trimming has a precise and easy description which makes it easy to include in a program that generates reliability models. This paper has presented the simplest version of the error bound for trimming. More accurate versions can be obtained by requesting more information about the system being modeled. For example, the current bound does not require any information about system recovery from

multiple faults. Conducting the necessary experiments and including this information in the derivation of the error can produce a tighter bound. The price of the tighter bound is the cost of the experiments.

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